

Horizon Europe

Data Management Plan

Version 1.0
26 February 2023

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	26.02.2023	Initial version

Action Number: 101040227

Action Acronym: WINGS

Action title: Winds In Galaxies

Date: 26/02/2023

DMP version: 1.0

1. Project Description

The WINGS project aims at mapping multi-phase outflows in the local and high-redshift Universe by exploiting the data acquired by multi-wavelength astronomical facilities.

2. Data Summary

Provenance of data	<p>The data are acquired by different telescopes, both ground- and space-based, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) ● Very Large Telescope (VLT) ● Atacama Large Millimeter Array (ALMA) <p>WINGS also exploit simulation data generated by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● collaborators ● Illustris TNG project
Storage	<p>All observational data are stored in public observatory archives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Southern Observatory Archive ● Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes <p>Simulation data are collected in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● a private collaborative platform with restricted access (username + password; authorised users only) ● public TNG project data archive (https://www.tng-project.org/data/)
Research products type	<p>Research products include (but are not limited to) observational studies spanning the electromagnetic spectrum from mm to near-IR</p>
Format of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● multi-dimensional data (.fits) ● tables (.csv; .txt) ● catalogues (.fits) ● binary (.hdf5)
Amount of data	<p>The size of each file is 10-100 GB</p>
Software requirements	<p>The following open-access softwares, tailored for astrophysical data analysis, are used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Common Astronomy Software Applications package ● SAOImageDS9 ● QFitsView ● Specviz ● Cubeviz ● open-access python packages: Astropy; Astroquery; Lmfit
Hardware requirements	<p>No specific hardware requirements are requested for the data analysis</p>
Data utility	<p>The data might be useful to the worldwide astronomical community</p>

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Any result obtained by WINGS will be published on [ArXiv/astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/astro-ph), which is the primary channel for disseminating astronomical research outcomes.

All science data products used for WINGS have associated metadata that provide users with details of interest. Indeed, the metadata meet the requirements of the astronomical Virtual Observatory (VO; <https://ivoa.net/>) that is an international data sharing framework which enables data to be FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable for the astronomers' needs.

FITS files include metadata in format of header keywords that enable users to assess the data quality and retrieve fundamental information of the science product, such as:

- the telescope and instruments used to obtain the data;
- the configuration of the instrument adopted during the experimental program;
- the reference data used to calibrate the data;
- the physical units and uncertainties of the data.

The metadata also include all the information that an archive user might want to search for in order to quickly select a dataset, compare several datasets, or discard a dataset.

Users can identify the data used in the WINGS project by using the following keywords:

- project code;
- source name;
- Principle Investigator's name;
- astronomical coordinates;
- start time and date of the observation in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC).

All scientific publications related to WINGS results will provide the aforementioned information in order to make the data findable and then re-use. The main keywords will also be reported on WINGS scientific report.

Some of the simulation data used in WINGS are collected in a private collaborative platform accessible to authorised users only. The scientific outputs, however, will be available to the entire community on the multidisciplinary repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

Simulated data from the TNG project are available to the the general research community and public on <https://www.tng-project.org/data/>. WINGS scientific publications that refer to those data will provide the keywords to retrieve the data.

3.2. Making data accessible

Observational data are stored in two major and trusted observatory archives based on the observational facility used to acquire them:

- European Southern Observatory Archive;
- Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes.

Data are collected in datasets that are indexed by using a unique set of keywords (see Section 3.1 of this data management plan) and a unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

The actual protocol for accessibility is taken care of by the observatory repository and infrastructures that offer data storage. Data and metadata are made openly available after an embargo period of 12 months. The embargo provides the Principal Investigator and any co-investigators who were awarded observation time on a telescope in

a competitive process with a proprietary period of time so they can work on the data before they are released to the general research community and public. The proprietary period for data and metadata is counted from the moment the files can be accessed and downloaded from the observatory archive. The release date of any embargoed file is set to the date of that event plus "the proprietary period" (i.e., 12 months).

In addition to the observatory archives, archive users may use libraries of astronomical catalogues (e.g., [VizieR](#)), providing tables and associated data published in academic journals or databases (e.g., [SIMBAD Astronomical Database](#)), providing information on astronomical objects of interest.

Science products collected in Zenodo repository are identified by a DOI and include metadata according to the VO standards. Datasets can be retrieved by using the Zenodo search.

3.3. Making data interoperable

Data and metadata used in WINGS are generated by using the VO standards that guarantee interoperability within and outside the astronomical community.

Data and metadata are stored in observatory archives that are involved in the International VO Alliance community and whose web portals provide direct search access to researchers, students, or any casual users. In addition to that, the programmatic search capabilities of those archives are available for interoperability with other research tools.

3.4. Increase data re-use

All data and metadata in the ESO and MAST observatory archive are distributed according to the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0). These products are available to the community for their use without restriction, provided that the product providers (i.e., principal investigator, ESO and MAST) are acknowledged in published works. If a user obtains such data and subsequently provides the data to a third party, the terms of the CC BY 4.0 license convey the data.

ESO and MAST subscribe to the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (see <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>).

Observatory archives are accessible through web interfaces that abide to virtual observatory standard protocols. These interfaces typically rely on the queries listed in Section 3.1 and use a "query, select, download" pattern for accessing files of the datasets.

Each dataset downloaded from the observatory archive is associated to a readme file, which provides a detailed description of the dataset including:

- the data quality;
- the open-access software used to calibrate the data;
- a description of data calibration process.

Observatory archives have also developed visualisation interfaces to display the data and assess their quality. These interfaces enable the visualisation of heterogeneous archival data, such as surveys, multi-dimensional data, catalogue data, and have the potential to provide a new level of interoperability between these different data types.

Finally, simulation data from the TNG project archive and science products in Zenodo are also distributed according to the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0).

4. Other research outputs

Softwares, source codes, and models developed in WINGS will be published and shared publicly on GitHub (<https://github.com/scarniani>) according to the terms of the GNU General Public License v3.0.

5. Allocation of resources

WINGS data and metadata are stored in observatory archives and multidisciplinary repository that guarantee long-term preservation at no cost to the project.

The project will benefit from four High Performance Computing (HPC) machines with heterogeneous capabilities available at the Scuola Normale Superiore. WINGS will only need an additional HPC machine, tailored to the data processing and analysis of the JWST, ALMA, and MUSE observations, whose costs are already covered as part of the project.

6. Data security

WINGS data, metadata, and science products will be stored in the European Southern Observatory Archive, Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes, and Zenodo that guarantee a long term and secure preservation and curation.

7. Ethics

WINGS does not require the collection of any personal data